

Servicewomen's Personal Traits

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Abstract: *The article reveals the theoretical substantiation and empirical research of the servicewomen's personal traits on the basis of theoretical analysis of scientific, methodological literature. A woman in order to perform military duties must have more or less muscular traits, such as stoutness, perseverance, determination, ability to manage, willingness to take risks, dominance, courage, propensity for leadership, organizational skills, self-sufficiency, independence, strength, and so on. The personal traits of women such as increased emotionality, softness, tactfulness, sensitivity, ability to empathize, tendency to intuitive comprehension of reality, clear maternal orientation have been substantiated. Psychological analysis of servicewomen professional activities indicates that most military service is influenced by such needs as success and power, a sense of social significance of service, participation in solving national problems, proving the value of one's own personality, self-affirmation through one's own career. Assessment of the personal qualities of women oriented to military service made it possible to determine that in the characteristics of this category dominate power, dominance, confidence, self-control, etc. It has been proven that the gender identity of servicewomen is the result of an active process that takes place continuously during ontogenesis and is accompanied by a person's sense of continuity, identity and certainty due to belonging to a certain individual unity. The analysis of the formal-dynamic properties of individuality revealed that, on average, female servicemen show themselves as active, purposeful, determined, with average overall mobility (in all spheres) and low sensitivity adapted to living conditions and military service.*

Keywords: *personality; gender; androgyny; femininity; masculinity; personal traits; female servicemen.*

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Introduction

A large number of women associate their lives with military service in the light of modern events, under the conditions of undeclared war, whereupon this fact has a significant impact not only upon their identification as women, but also upon the formation of relationships in families, society, the country as a whole. One of the most important problems in creating a harmonious relationship between a man and a woman is a relationship based on complementarity, and that is exactly why the issues of gender and gender characteristics thrust to the fore.

The increase in the number of women in the Armed Forces of the states has contributed to the intensification of scientific research on the problems of servicewomen. The military aspect of women's social issues was studied in the second half of the last century by American and Western European researchers. It was during this period that special works appeared on the role of women in the army. "The analysis of the state of the modern information society in Ukraine testifies that the whole system, all types of social relations are undergoing changes, which leads to the search for their own way, to the development and change of values in both men and women" (Matokhnyuk, 2018).

Analysis of recent research and publications. Gender studies have developed quite widely since the early 90's of the twentieth century. Insufficient attention is paid to gender issues in the Armed Forces of Ukraine nowadays. Studies of various aspects of the personality of a serviceman of the Ukrainian army became popular in the early 1990s. Some scholars also studied the problems of permanent officers, soldiers, and sergeants of compulsory military service. M. Tomchuk considered methodological analysis of the problem of scientific knowledge and purposeful formation of psychological readiness of an individual for activity in his works (Tomchuk, 2011). Some details on military specialists training issues of different specialties and genders can be also found in the works of (Karpushyna et al., 2019; Bloshchynskyi, 2017a; 2017b).

Other scholars, namely I. Bloshchynskyi, O. Halus, I. Pochekalin, and D. Taushan described the use of electronic educational and methodological software packages for improving the preparation of the cadets of different genders for final examinations (2018). Regarding neuropedagogical issues some authors examined foreign students' intercultural adaptation experience that depends on effective interpersonal communication in order to determine the main problems of adaptation from

physiological, socio-psychological, sociocultural, academic points of view (Bilotserkovets et al., 2020). Some researchers L. Herasymenko, S. Muravska, S. Radul, & O. Pidlubna defined the effect of teaching critical thinking skills to future pilots in the framework of Aviation English. First year student pilots, who took part in the study, were chosen based on their level of English proficiency and critical thinking skills, age, and gender (Herasymenko et al., 2019).

Concerning neuropsychological researches some scholars investigated differences in the formation of personality traits for children with various language disorders and children who do not have language disorders from a neuropsychological perspective in urban areas (Pânișoară et al., 2019). Other scholars G. Pânișoară, I. Pânișoară, C. Sandu & R. Chirca (Neacșu) studied the status of positive psychology strengths within the Romanian school in the digital society and identified the possible correlations between the strengths that are taught in school and those which are necessary for reaching personal success. The subjects selected for this research were 100 teachers from Romania, both male and female (2017). In the article of R. Valieiev, V. Polyvaniuk, T. Antonenko, M. Rebkalo, A. Sobakar, & V. Oliinyk, authors determined the level of Ukrainian police officers' burnout and effect of gender, tenure and primary workplace (field work or office service) on it. As for the police officers' sample, which included 129 men (70.1%) and 55 women (29.9%), gender was presented as a dichotomous variable, female (1) or male (2). Officers represented nine various departments from 18 regions of Ukraine (2019).

The purpose of the article. In view of this, the purpose of the work is to theoretically substantiate and empirically research the servicewomen's personal traits.

Methodology of Research

Theoretical foundations of the research.

A human personality is an extremely deep concept. It is formed under the influence of psychological and social factors. Personality consists of features and psychological traits that are combined in its individuality or originality, which distinguishes it from other people. It is manifested in the traits of temperament, character, habits, as cognitive processes and so on. According to the scientists, the concept of personality can be interpreted from different points of view, namely: O. Leontiev "Personality is a set of social relations implemented in various activities", S. Rubinstein "Personality is a set of internal conditions through which all external influences are

refracted”, B. Ananiev “Personality is the subject of social behaviour and communication”, K. Platonov “Personality is a human being who is the bearer of consciousness” and others (Matokhnyuk, 2019). Therefore, the concept of personality can be interpreted as consisting of features and psychological traits that are combined in its individuality and distinguishes it from other people. Stereotypical understanding of gender, differences between men and women and various prejudices about their relationships in the social and interpersonal spheres have been formed for millennia.

Peculiarities of gender and sex psychology have attracted many researchers of personality psychology. There is virtually none of the known theories of personality, which would not consider the laws of male and female psychology as characteristics of the essence of personality. “The interpretation of the peculiarities of the development of men and women was radically revised under the influence of feminist ideas of the XVIII-XIX centuries, which significantly served to distinguish gender research as an independent scientific field in the social sciences” (Tkalych, 2011).

The concepts of gender are often identified with the concepts of sex, but these are completely different concepts. Comparative characteristics of the concepts of “sex” and “gender” are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Comparative characteristics of the concepts of “sex” and “gender”

Term	Sex	Gender
Definition of concept	Biological, anatomical, physiological differences between a man and a woman, which provide the reproductive functions of the body	Social characteristics of being a woman, a man, a girl, a boy which are expected, allowed and valued
Origin	Inherited with sex	Acquired in society i.e. the gender is being taught and it is prepared for various social roles, behaviours, activities, based on gender
Social manifestations	Similar in different countries	Various in different countries, depending on place of residence or social status
Invariance	Invariable characteristics	Variable with time and place

Characteristic traits of women are passed on from generation to generation in hereditary traits, i.e. inherited through maternal and paternal gametes, which contain a complete set of genetic information, stored and

reproduced as the main features of external and internal structure, physicochemical features and vital functions, are consolidated in the process of ontogenesis by combining the influence of hereditary information and society (micro- and macro-environment) and have a significant impact upon the identification of women according to social status and the roles they play.

The main purpose of studying the professional activity of this category of women is the need to determine the socio-economic and sanitary-hygienic characteristics of the military profession, to determine the requirements it places on psychophysiological and personal characteristics of women, i.e. to outline a set of professionally important traits.

The concept of “military activity” and its synonym “military service” are disclosed as a specific socially necessary type of activity, which includes military training, operational readiness, sentry, guard, internal service, maintenance, inspection and repair of military hardware, direct combat operations and actions (Armed Forces Field Manuals, 1999). However, as M. Tomchuk rightly noted in his study, this definition of military service is much broader than military activity, as it covers not only elements of military and service activity, but also elements of communal activity and service work, recreation, leisure, etc. (Tomchuk, 2011).

Results of Research

Servicewomen must have the following psychophysiological parameters as the ability to communicate with people and regulate their behaviour, the desire to be a leader, the ability to lead, to have strong willpower, to be willing to take reasonable risks, to strive for success, to be ambitious, to be able to dominate in extreme conditions, to be self-sufficient, to have a combinatorial-prognostic type of thinking. They have to possess personal traits such as extensive knowledge, energetic capacity, self-confidence, righteousness in taken decisions, purposefulness, tactfulness, efficiency, exactingness, censoriousness, flexibility, creativity, high organizational skills, competence, broad outlook, proactive attitude, self-control, responsibility, persistence, self-control, rapport, resoluteness, the need for achievements, patience and correctness.

They also have to possess a high level of general intelligence and a high level of verbal abilities. The women have to know and be able to perform service functional responsibilities in peacetime and in special periods; requirements of the guideline papers regulating the issues of the military service planning and organization (according to the specifics of the service); the order of planning and organization of support in a special

period (according to the specifics of the service); the procedure for planning and carrying out measures of complete mobilization and bring the unit into combat readiness; the order of planning, organization and accounting of combat training, forms and methods of personnel training; the main provisions and requirements of the Field Manuals of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, orders and directives for strengthening military discipline, maintaining the statutory order, clear organization of routine military duty and medical care; the order of all types of support of the unit; means and property used in the unit; the order of observance of safety rules during trainings, exercises, range practices; the procedure for providing self-help and mutual assistance in all emergencies.

As for psychological characteristics, a servicewoman definitely needs to be in good health, because she is obliged to be ready to undertake functional responsibilities under any weather conditions, at any time of the day or night. She can only afford a sparse, short rest, which is usually disrupted.

Due to the above circumstances, she should be as insensitive to weather conditions as possible. A servicewoman must have good immunity since she often has to deal with various infectious diseases. The requirements for the nervous system are extremely high: irregular lifestyle (untimely meals, disturbed night rest), anxiety and heavy responsibility of the profession, suppressing the impression of human suffering, and finally the insecurity of her own material existence. Strong leg muscles are desirable for servicewomen who wear military uniforms and perform duties over long distances; and considerable arm strength is required in many cases, such as carrying weapons, bulletproof vests, and carrying over patients during an evacuation. A “sensual nature” is not very suitable for military activities associated with frequent depressing experiences. In their activities, they often find themselves in a kind of unpleasant situation (for example, performing duties within the joint forces operations zone, during armed hostilities). In these cases, they should not show cowardice or subjective bias that interfere with the performance of their professional duties, should not attach much importance to external habits and a certain way of life, because their activities constantly force them to disrupt this way of life.

In all emergencies, they must take immediate actions. The person who get tired quickly is not at all suitable for such activities (for example, within the joint forces operations zone), which require continuous work from morning until night. They have to make quick decisions in situations of extreme gravity or urgency.

Sociologist Y. Miliuska notes that when considering the conditions for the formation of signs of gender in women, we must take into account three levels of phenomena that can explain and influence this process: biological (possibilities of functioning due to structural and functional capabilities of the body), psychological (a resource that a woman uses to construct her own identity) and social (dominant ideology and social changes in society) (Tkalych et al., 2020).

We can conclude that gender behaviour is formed in the process of influence of various factors with the following distinguished groups:

- hereditary factors (a set of hereditary material containing the human genome, which in turn consists of 23 pairs of chromosomes (22 pairs of autosomes and 1 pair of sex ones), i.e. in general the human genome contains 20-25 thousand active genes).

- physiological manifestations (factors related to physiology, body structure, genitals, the peculiarity of the functioning of various organs and systems, endocrine profile, attractiveness, criteria for assessing the appearance of men and women).

- local macro-environment (the impact of one's close environment, family upon the human body from early childhood i.e. the example of the mother, her behaviour, her role, family relationships, consolidation of family roles, etc.).

- global macro-environment (the impact of society, environment, gender stereotypes in the country, social behaviour, consolidation of social and professional roles, etc.).

Once formed, gender identity is manifested in the form of gender behaviour, in the study of which there are such basic components as masculinity, femininity and androgyny. Sex and gender roles are closely linked to a person's gender identity. P. Hornostai emphasizes the following: "the features of role socialization are not only in the assimilation of social expectations concerning social roles, but also in the formation of psychological roles, both personal and social (Hornostay, 2004).

The environment, in particular the professional one, in some way affects the consolidation or development of a woman's traits that she needs to perform certain social and professional roles (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Model of servicewomen gender manifestation
[Systematized by the authors]

Views upon the relationship between the concepts of androgyny, femininity and masculinity have changed, but their essence has always

remained the same – they reflect the accepted social behaviour of men and women. Femininity is the characteristics of the female sex or the characteristic forms of behaviour expected of a woman in a given society (Anthony Giddens), or the social expression of what is seen as a woman's intrinsic positions (Lisa Tuttle). Femininity is not a purely feminine trait, as it has become entrenched in our consciousness, overloaded with various stereotypes, but a certain way of understanding and perception of reality. Characteristic features of femininity are emotionality, sensitivity, intuitive cognition. The notion of gender identity as a social sex is closely related to the issue of femininity, as a woman who enters the social environment changes it. She introduces a different way of thinking and acting, new content and new forms of execution. A woman leaves the private sphere for the social one, expands the sphere of her self-realization and enriches social reality with her way of perceiving reality (Doronina, 2014).

Feminist studies have denied the conditionality of sociocultural characteristics and processes by biological differences: femininity is not so much natural as formed from childhood. According to French theorists of feminism (Six, Julia Kristeva), femininity is an arbitrary category given to women by patriarchy.

There is also the idea that femininity is a special “equal-but-different” polarity of masculinity, which is also wrong, because masculine traits (endurance, stoutness, self-sufficiency) are valuable for all people, i.e. both for women and men, and feminine ones are desirable for women only in terms of their attractiveness to men. The concept of androgyny is a combination of male and female in one person (Titarenko, 2003).

Then everyone chooses his/her own way of life that is traditional male one (focused on the manifestation of masculinity i.e. independence, achievement, dominance), purely male virtues and values (courage, strength, bravery, aggression, imperturbability) and social male roles (breadwinner, protector, guardian, leader) or vice versa feminine one with signs of flexibility, shyness, sensitivity, tenderness, femininity, ability to empathize, avoiding risks, management and control.

The constant fulfilment of these social and family roles cultivates and reinforces in a person the traits that are necessary for their fulfilment.

All these and similar examples are united by the fact that people define themselves within the dimensions of masculinity-femininity not in their pure form, but in a mixture of both. However, the predominance of masculinity in women hinders the formation of quality relationships in the family that is a woman-leader rarely assigns the responsibilities of a leader to her husband. That is why, if during the performance of social and family

roles one would rely upon femininity, which is laid down genetically, then in the future a woman can choose another social and family role for herself.

The length of service of servicewomen has some effect upon the manifestation of gender identity of these women and reinforces the gender identity manifestation that has called a woman for military official responsibilities.

Thus, the results of a thorough analysis of literature sources and current legislation suggest that military service is a socially significant activity aimed at ensuring the sovereignty of the Ukrainian state, its territorial integrity and inviolability and is carried out on a voluntary basis by specific methods and means; professional activity; complex type of activity, characterized by special conditions; has a large list of necessary mental and professional qualities for successful performance of tasks on purpose.

There are a number of studies of gender issues in the modern psychological literature. An empirical study of the gender identity of the selected sample group has been started upon a detailed review of the theoretical material, analysis of the scientific literature, classification, systematization and generalization of the information obtained. The survey methods included a questionnaire i.e. collecting criminological information by filling in pre-designed questionnaires, testing, psychodiagnostic methods such as: Freiburg's personal questionnaire - Sandra Bem's "Masculinity – Femininity" scale; "Orientation to Traditional or Egalitarian Relations" test (in the family) (according to the description of I. Kliotsyna); Minnesota multidisciplinary personality questionnaire or MMPI method (scale 5); questionnaire of formal-dynamic properties of personality by V. Rusalov (QFDPP); methods of diagnosis of interpersonal relationships by T. Leary.

The questionnaire survey allowed determining the age of the surveyed women and the length of their military service, and the impact of these indicators upon the level of gender identity manifestation.

Freiburg's questionnaire, in particular Sandra Bem's "Masculinity – Femininity" method, found that 70% of servicewomen were women with androgyny manifestation, 18% were masculine and only 12% feminine. Correlation analysis of gender manifestation and length of service showed that there is a close positive relationship between these indicators. Having examined the level of focus upon traditional or egalitarian relations it can be concluded that the majority of servicewomen are oriented towards egalitarian relations making 64% of respondents, while 36% of respondents prefer traditional relations. Based on the correlation analysis (taking into account the results of the Pearson correlation coefficient), it is concluded that there is a close positive relationship between the manifestation of

gender identity and the focus upon traditional or egalitarian relations, i.e. the focus upon egalitarian relations with equal family rights and responsibilities is prevailing. The use of Timothy Leary method of interpersonal relationships diagnosis made it possible to explore women's perceptions of themselves and the ideal "Ego". The women recruited for military service have prevailing dominance indicator making 2.452, and the friendliness indicator makes 1.284, which confirms the shift of gender identity towards masculinity and androgyny.

Assessment of personal traits of women focused upon military service revealed that the characterological peculiarities of this category are dominated by power, dominance, confidence, self-control, etc., with a fairly high indicator of willingness to come to the rescue.

The analysis of formal-dynamic properties of individuality allowed to determine that servicewomen show themselves on average as active, purposeful, decisive, with average indicators of general mobility (in all spheres) and low sensitivity indicators, adapted to living conditions and military service.

Conclusions

On the grounds of theoretical analysis, it has been determined that gender identity is a social sex, cultural product or socio-biological characteristic that indicates the social status and socio-psychological characteristics of the individual, which are related to sex and sexuality, but arise in interaction with other people, taking into account primary, secondary and tertiary sexual characteristics, by which people define the concepts of "male" and "female".

On the grounds of theoretical analysis, the personal traits of women have been highlighted, such as increased emotionality, softness, tactfulness, sensitivity, ability to empathize, tendency to intuitive comprehension of reality, clear maternal orientation. It has been proven that the gender identity of servicewomen is the result of an active process that takes place continuously during ontogenesis and is accompanied by a person's sense of continuity, identity and certainty due to belonging to a certain individual unity.

Psychological analysis of servicewomen professional activities indicates that most military service is influenced by such needs as success and power, a sense of social significance of service, participation in solving national problems, proving the value of one's own personality, self-affirmation through one's own career. Since military activity is intense and extreme one compared to other activities, it is characterized by surprise,

suddenness, unusualness, the ability to destroy existing stereotypes of behaviour, create negative mental states (anxiety, fear, affect, stress, depression), so a woman in order to perform military duties must have more or less muscular traits, such as stoutness, perseverance, determination, ability to manage, willingness to take risks, dominance, courage, propensity for leadership, organizational skills, self-sufficiency, independence, strength, and so on.

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